

Binary Systems of Mesogens and Non-mesogens exhibiting Mesomorphism

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Liquid crystal formation in eight binary systems are reported in which one or both the components are non-mesogens. The binary systems of non-mesogens, comprising of components with terminal nitro or chloro substituent, exhibit induced smectic or nematic mesophases; induction of mesophase is higher in magnitude for a nitro group as compared to a chloro group. Shorter alkyl/alkoxy chains are not conducive to the mixed mesomorphism, probably due to lack of marked depression in melting points. The systems incorporating a monotropic mesogen and a non-mesogen, exhibit mesomorphic properties comparable with the binary systems of non-mesogens of the present work. Some of the binary compositions exhibit smectic phase at ambient temperature on cooling. The latent transition temperatures for non-mesogens are obtained and the phase diagrams are discussed in detail.

The review of mixed liquid crystals studies reveals that a mesogen or a non-mesogen is added to low melting mesogens, either to decrease the melting point or to increase the mesophase range or to change the electric conductivity and dielectric anisotropy¹. Dave *et al.*² studied some binary systems comprising of a smectogen and non-mesogenic Schiff base. Vora and Chhangawala³ and George *et al.*⁴ reported binary systems of a polymorphic smectogen and a non-mesogenic Schiff base, where they observed the induced nematic mesophase. Ziemnicka *et al.*⁵ and Neubert *et al.*⁶ reported the creation of nematic phase in smectogen by the addition of the second component which is also a mesogen. Shashidhar *et al.*⁷ for the first time observed a new kind of smectic A-A transition in binary mixtures of terminally substituted cyano and nitro compounds. Gupta and Vora⁸ and Bangarraju *et al.*⁹ studied the binary systems of mesogenic and non-mesogenic compounds.

In the present study eight binary systems in which one or both the compounds are non-mesogenic in nature have been studied. The systems have either two ester components or an ester and a Schiff base with nitro or chloro terminal groups. Induced nematic and smectic mesophases have been observed in the six binary systems over a wide concentration range.

Results and Discussion

The following compounds were used as components for all the binary systems.

Type-I

- (i) PABB; R = C₅H₁₁, R' = CH(CH₃)₂
- (ii) PHBB; R = C₇H₁₅, R' = CH(CH₃)₂
- (iii) EBBB; R = C₄H₉, R' = C₂H₅

Type-II

- (iv) BBCB; R = C₄H₉, Z = Cl
- (v) BBCB; R = C₅H₁₁, Z = Cl
- (vi) BBNB; R = C₄H₉, Z = NO₂

- (vii) NBPA; X = NO₂, Y = OC₅H₁₁
- (viii) NBHA; X = NO₂, Y = OC₆H₁₃
- (ix) ACA; X = OCH₃, Y = Cl

The present work incorporates following two types of binary systems.

Type-I : In this type, both the components are non-mesogens. Six binary systems were studied, out of which four systems exhibit induced smectic and nematic mesophases. One of the components is an ester while the other is either an ester or a Schiff base possessing a nitro or a chloro group.

System Ia (PABB : NBHA) : The binary phase diagram (Fig. 1) exhibits an induced monotropic

Fig. 1 System Ia, (●) mesomorphic, (○) isotropic-nematic and (Δ) smectic-isotropic.

nematic phase at 19 mole percent concentration of PABB and enantiotropic smectic phase between 30 and 80 mole percent concentration of PABB. In the region where system exhibits enantiotropic smectic mesophase, the crystal to mesomorphic transition temperatures are much depressed.

System Ib (PABB : NBPA) : The binary phase diagram (Fig. 2) exhibits an induced monotropic nematic phase between 11 and 19 mole percent concentration of PABB. In the system nematic mesophase is enhanced as compared to system Ia. This may be attributed to the shorter alkoxy chain length of NBPA, as all other features of the systems are the same. The induced smectic mesophase is observed between 29 and 79 mole percent of PABB. Some of the binary compositions exhibit smectic mesophase at ambient temperature on cooling.

System Ic (EBBB : ABCB) : The system is comprised of 'compatible' i.e. both the components

Fig. 2. System Ib : (●) mesomorphic, (○) isotropic-nematic and (Δ) smectic-isotropic

Fig. 3. System Ic : (●) isotropic, (○) nematic-isotropic and (Δ) nematic-smectic

are esters. The phase diagram (Fig. 3) exhibits an induced nematic and smectic mesophases in the concentration range 29–38 mole percent of EBBB. The binary system is far less mesogenic as compared to the systems Ia and Ib. The systems Ia and Ib have ester and Schiff base as the components. It has been observed⁸ that the ester and Schiff base linkages are incompatible, hence depression in melting points will be of greater magnitude in the binary mixtures. In the case of system Ic, both the components are esters, hence structures are compatible. Moreover, the aliphatic ester chain is shorter and a chloro substituent is present in place of a nitro group. The overall effect of all these factors results in poor mesogenic behaviour of the system.

System Id (EBBB : BBNB) : This binary system differs from system **Ic**, in that the chloro terminal substituent is replaced by a nitro group. The phase diagram (Fig. 4) exhibits an induced smectic and

Fig 4 System **Id** (●) isotropic, (○) nematic-isotropic and (△) nematic-smectic

nematic mesophases over a wide concentration range of 28–78 mole percent of EBBB. This is a striking difference between system **Ic** and **Id** and this phenomenon can only be attributed to the presence of the nitro group. From the mesogenic behaviour of the two systems it can be concluded that the nitro group is more conducive to the mixed mesomorphism as compared to the chloro group, and can induce mesomorphism in the binary systems having components with 'compatible' structure. This observation also corroborates our earlier work¹⁰.

System Ie (PABB : ACA) and If (PBT : ABCB) : The binary system **Ie** is comprised of components having 'incompatible' structure. No mesomorphism is observed in the mixed state (Fig. 5). In the system **Ic**, it was observed that chloro group is less conducive to mixed mesomorphism. In the system **Ie**, the combination of short alkoxy chain and terminal chloro group eliminates mesomorphism. Similarly, system **If** also does not exhibit any mesomorphism (Fig. 6). The two components have 'compatible' structure, but one of the components has a shorter alkyl chain and no mesomorphism is observed.

From the systems **Ic**, **Ie** and **If** it can be concluded

Fig 5 System **Ie** (●) isotropic

that in a binary mixtures of nonmesogens, chloro group is less conducive to mixed mesomorphism as compared to a nitro group and to observe mesophases in such systems, components must possess alkoxy/alkyl chains of adequate length.

Type-II : In this type one of the components is non-mesogenic and the other is monotropic smectic. Two binary systems of this type were studied. One of the components is non-mesogenic Schiff base while the other is an ester exhibiting monotropic smectic phase only on quenching.

System IIa (PHBB · NBHA) : The behaviour of the system is very interesting, with as low concentration as 9.7 mole percent of PHBB, induced monotropic nematic phase is observed (Fig. 7). The monotropic smectic phase becomes enantiotropic between 29 and 88 mole percent of PHBB. The region where system exhibits enantiotropic smectic mesophase, the crystal to smectic transition temperatures are much more depressed and the curve becomes almost a parabola. The smectic phase is exhibited at room temperature by certain mixed liquid crystal compositions on cooling. The smectic-isotropic curve shows a falling tendency from left to right.

The nematic-isotropic transition temperature curve is extrapolated on the side where nematic phase is observed. The latent transition temperature obtained for NBHA by this method is 88°, which is in very good agreement with our earlier work⁸.

Fig 6 System II (●) isotropic

System IIIb (PHBB : NBPA) : The binary phase diagram (Fig. 8) exhibits that with as low concentration as 8.0 mole percent of PHBB, induced nematic mesophase is observed, which persists upto about 20 mole percent of PHBB. At the same concentration monotropic smectic phase is observed which becomes enantiotropic between 28 and 75 mole percent of PHBB. In the region where enantiotropic smectic phase is observed, the crystal-smectic transition temperatures are very much depressed. In some of the mixed liquid crystal compositions the smectic phase is stable at ambient temperature on cooling. The nematic-isotropic curve is extrapolated to find the latent transition temperature of the non-mesogen.

Fig 7 System IIIa : (●) mesomorphic or isotropic, (○) nematic-isotropic or isotropic-nematic and (Δ) smectic-isotropic or isotropic-smectic

Fig 8 System IIIb : (●) mesomorphic or isotropic, (○) nematic-isotropic or isotropic-nematic and (Δ) smectic-isotropic or isotropic-smectic

The latent transition temperature obtained for NBPA by this method is 80° which agrees with our earlier work⁸.

Conclusion : The present work indicates that in the binary systems where none of the components are mesogenic in nature, induced mesomorphism can be observed, both with the 'incompatible' and 'compatible' structures of components, though the range of stability of mesophases are lower for compatible structures. The study also reveals that the nitro group enhances the induced mesophases as compared to the chloro group. If the chainlength of alkyl/alkoxy group is adequate, induced mesophases can be obtained in binary systems having a terminal chloro group.

Experimental

The following compounds were synthesised by known methods : (A) isopropyl (*p*-*n*-heptyloxybenzoyloxy)benzoate¹¹ (PHBB), (B) isopropyl (*p*-*n*-amyloxybenzoyloxy)benzoate¹¹ (PABB), (C) ethyl (*p*-*n*-butoxybenzoyloxy)benzoate¹¹ (EBBB), (D) *p*-nitrobenzylidene-*p*'-*n*-pentyloxyaniline¹² (NBPA), (E) *p*-nitrobenzylidene-*p*'-hexyloxyansaline¹² (NBHA), (F) *p*-(*p*'-*n*-amyloxybenzoyloxy)nitrobenzene¹³ (ABCB), (G) *p*-(*p*'-*n*-butoxy)nitrobenzene¹⁴ (BBNB), (H) *p*-(*p*'-*n*-amyloxybenzoyloxy)toluene¹⁵ (PBT) and (I) *p*-anisal-*p*-chloroaniline¹⁶ (ACA).

The elemental analysis of all the compounds were found satisfactory.

Preparation of mixtures : Both the components were weighed accurately in known proportions and fused together in fusion tubes. The components were thoroughly mixed to obtain a homogeneous mixture. The melt was quenched and the solid obtained was finely ground and used for determining the transition temperatures. The transition temperatures were determined by using Leitz Laborlux 12 POL microscope.

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